

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck found at Dyngö, Sweden.

by

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Samples from a shipwreck found at Dyngö, Sweden, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. The results of the dendrochronological analysis are described in this report.

Fig. 1. Dyngö, Sweden. The chronological position of the dated samples from the wreck.

Seven samples from the wreck are listed. They are all oak (*Quercus* sp.). The planks that the samples are taken from are tangentially converted from the parent tree, and some cracking of the preserved timbers caused splitting of samples.

Samples 1 and 2 were probably from the same plank. The tree-ring growth of sample 2 presents as very distorted, as it is taken at a large knot in the timber. The tree-ring curves from these two are so similar, that the dendrochronology can confirm that these two samples are indeed from the same timber. The tree-ring curve from this timber (Z312001_2) is 128 years long. The plank samples have 9 sapwood years. This plank is dated. It is from a tree felled AD 1226-41.

Sample 3 was in two pieces. Both pieces were measured. The tree-ring curve from this timber (Z3120039) is 162 years long, only heartwood is observed. This timber is dated. It is from a tree felled after AD 1232.

Sample 4 is from a small plank fragment. It contains 55 tree-rings, all heartwood. The tree-ring curve from this sample matches so well with sample 5, that these two samples might be from the same tree.

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Sample 5 is in two parts. Both samples were measured. The tree-ring curves from sample 4 and 5 are averaged to one (Z3120059) and this is 147 years in length. Twenty-two sapwood rings were observed on this plank sample. This plank is also dated. It is from a tree felled AD 1233-40.

Sample 6 is from part of a scarf or repair piece. It contains 67 tree-rings, all heartwood. It is dated, and it is from a tree felled after AD 1215. As there is no sapwood on this sample it cannot be suggested or proven whether it is an original or a repair piece.

Sample 7 (Z312007a) is also part of a scarf or repair. It contains 37 tree-rings and could not be dated. If it is part of sample 6 this cannot be shown through the dendrochronological analysis, due to the very few rings in this sample.

Combining the results from all dated samples and assuming that the planks are from trees felled at the same time, we can suggest that the felling of these trees took place in the period AD 1233-1240 (marked with green in fig. 1).

All the timbers are tangentially converted planks, and knots in the trees can be seen in the material. The grain of the wood was distorted in places. It was not possible to discern any saw marks in the preserved surface, but it can be assumed that tangential planks were sawn, as a rule.

		Z3120039 s3	Z312006a s6	Z312001_2 s1s2	Z3120059 s5s4
Average Z312M001	Z3120039 s3	*	3.99	3.08	3.23
	Z312006a s6	3.99	*	4.37	3.85
	Z312001_2 s1s2	3.08	4.37	*	4.03
	Z3120059 s5s4	3.23	3.85	4.03	*

Table 1. Dyngö, Sweden. The correlation between the tree-ring curves of all dated timbers and each other.

Provenance

The tree-ring curves from the four dated timbers cross-date with each other as shown in table 1. An average of all four is made (Z312M001) of 178 years in length. The correlation between this mean curve and diverse Northern European tree-ring datasets for oak is shown in table 2. The highest correlations appear with chronologies from Lower Saxony (see table 2).

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) in which the calculation of the t -value (" t -test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is embedded. To calculate the felling date for the dated samples a sapwood average for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) is utilised. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted.

Filenames	-	-	Z312M001	
-	start	dates	AD1055	
-	dates	end	AD1232	
Master and site chronologies				
G350PZ01	AD967	AD1381	10.35	Truhen 46 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
DM200005	AD915	AD1873	10.07	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni)
DM200006	AD914	AD1873	10.04	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)
00000059	AD1101	AD1350	8.63	Svendborg Denmark (Bartholin pers comm)
ofrmitde	AD300	AD1200	8.26	O.Friestl. middenstuk 1995 (Jansma pers comm)
dk west	152BC	AD1996	7.74	DK West (Nationalmuseet)
F021m001	AD1132	AD1234	7.63	Kristinebjerg Øst brønd 2 timbers (Daly 2009)
E017M001	AD1040	AD1251	7.57	Tønder Rådhus 3 timbers (Daly 2014)
DM100006st	AD851	AD1293	7.25	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
G351WZ01	AD1084	AD1354	7.15	Sudenburg 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
H11JPM01	AD946	AD1241	7.14	HL Fischstr. 36 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	7.07	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
G370GZ01	AD970	AD1256	7.02	Ihlow 11 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
D0137M02	AD1057	AD1202	6.71	TBT Odense group2 3 timbers (Daly & Daly 2019)
G312MZ01	AD1041	AD1243	6.48	Einbeck II 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
H200KM02	AD1022	AD1259	6.45	hbg. Grabung 5 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
G340UZ01	AD1112	AD1253	6.42	Braunschweig 7 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
D0137M03A	AD1127	AD1310	6.16	TBT Odense group3A 6 timbers (Daly & Daly 2019)
30079M01	AD998	AD1374	6.16	Stegeborg all 26 timbers (Daly 2001c)
70314M04	AD953	AD1198	6.09	Skjern Bro 9 timbers (Daly 2001b 2006)
DD001M000	AD1005	AD1338	6.01	Altenkirchen (Bartholin pers comm)
DM200001	AD1082	AD1972	5.99	Nieders. Kuestenraum (Göttingen Uni)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	5.98	Ålborg Østerå & Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000b 2001a)
P676001m	AD1084	AD1393	5.96	Poland Kolobrzeg (Wazny pers comm)
DM200004	30BC	AD1960	5.80	G Weser (Göttingen Uni)
GBM00005	AD413	AD1654	5.79	London Big mean (Sheffield Uni)
DM100008	AD457	AD1723	5.70	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
Chronologies from ships				
doel1_all_m2	AD1150	AD1305	7.56	Ship timbers Doel 1 (Haneca & Daly 2014)
Z0071M21 a	AD1099	AD1378	6.73	Bremen 44 timbers (Daly 2017b; Belasus et al 2021)
Z169M001	AD1055	AD1244	6.06	Kalve Rev Storstrømmen vrøg 5 timbers (Daly 2017a)
0099M004	AD903	AD1205	5.66	Møllestrømmen 7 timbers (Daly 2000a 2015)

Table 2. Dyngö. Result of the correlation between the average curve from the samples from the wreck and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

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Catalogue

filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	conversion	extra end	ave ring width mm	interpretation / felling
Dyngö											
Z312001_2 s1s2	Dyngö cog s1s2 plank QUSP	128	AD1093	AD1220	G	9	N	T	S1	1.57	AD1226-41
Z3120039 s3	Dyngö cog s3 plank QUSP	162	AD1055	AD1216	F	0	N	T	H1	1.14	after AD1232
Z312004a s4	Dyngö cog s4 plank small fragment QUSP	55	AD1114	AD1168	G	0	N	T	H1	1.93	Same tree as s5
Z3120059 s5s4	Dyngö cog s5+4 plank QUSP	147	AD1086	AD1232	G	22	N	T	S1	1.35	AD1233-40
Z312006a s6	Dyngö cog s6 plank QUSP	67	AD1133	AD1199	G	0	N	T	H1	3.24	after AD1215
Z312007a	Dyngö cog s7 plank QUSP	37			G	0	N	T	H1	2.91	undated
Averages											
Z312M001	Dyngö cog 4 timbers QUSP	178	AD1055	AD1232						1.55	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp./Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch											
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